

Multidisciplinary Pathways into Cyber Threat Intelligence Roles: Mapping Knowledge Areas and Transferable Skills

Christos Kallonas¹[0009-0001-8747-545X], Stavros Stavrou¹[0000-0002-3189-9421], and Eliana Stavrou¹[0000-0003-4040-494]

¹ Open University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus
christos.kallonas@st.ouc.ac.cy, stavros.stavrou@ouc.ac.cy,
eliana.stavrou@ouc.ac.cy

Abstract. Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) has emerged as a critical field within cybersecurity, enabling organizations to proactively detect, assess, and respond to evolving digital threats. Traditionally perceived as a technically intensive field, CTI increasingly demands a broader set of competencies that extend beyond the confines of traditional sciences that are relevant to CTI. Such competencies include behavioral analysis, geopolitical awareness, investigative thinking, and effective communication. As the threat landscape grows more complex and intertwined with social, political, and psychological dimensions, there is a growing need to clearly establish the disciplinary foundations that can support the CTI profession. This study addresses this need by investigating the multidisciplinary nature of CTI, identifying which academic disciplines outside traditional technical fields can contribute to CTI practice and how. The investigations identified five academic disciplines (criminology, psychology, political science, journalism, and data science) as having potential relevance to CTI. Using these disciplines as a basis, the study investigated their alignment with core CTI knowledge areas and transferable skills identified as part of the investigations, drawing on two skills frameworks: ENISA's European Cybersecurity Skills Framework and Mandiant's CTI Analyst Core Competencies Framework. The findings offer insights into how diverse academic backgrounds can support CTI functions, challenge existing assumptions about career pathways into CTI, and propose future research directions for developing more inclusive and multidisciplinary training strategies. In doing so, the study contributes to a growing body of research advocating for a multidisciplinary approach to cybersecurity workforce development, where diverse expertise is recognized as a strength rather than an exception.

Keywords: Cyber Threat Intelligence, CTI, Competency mapping, Cybersecurity workforce development, ECSF, Multidisciplinary pathways, Transferable skills, Talent, Cybersecurity education.

1 Introduction

As cyber threats grow in scale, complexity, and impact, organizations are increasingly turning to Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) for enhancing their security posture. CTI encompasses the collection, analysis, and dissemination of threat-related information to inform decision-making across tactical, operational, and strategic levels [1][2]. The intelligence produced serves an array of functions, from detecting indicators of compromise to profiling threat actors and informing national security strategies. This diverse set of functions reflects not only a technological evolution but also a fundamental transformation in the competencies required for CTI professionals [3][4].

Recent literature increasingly highlights that technical expertise alone is not enough to support effective CTI. Researchers and practitioners argue that there is a growing need to include a wide range of knowledge and skills from several academic and professional fields [5]. CTI roles now require skills in behavioral analysis, open-source research, intelligence reporting, understanding international affairs, and knowledge of legal systems [6][7][8]. Such skills are commonly developed in disciplines such as criminology, psychology, law, political science, and journalism. Although these fields have not traditionally been part of cybersecurity training, they are increasingly recognized as essential to performing CTI tasks effectively [9][10].

This broader view of CTI as a combination of multiple disciplines has led researchers to start exploring how professionals from non-IT disciplines can contribute to the field. Recent studies indicate promising results, identifying that professionals with strong reasoning skills, the ability to communicate clearly, and a good understanding of social or organizational contexts can successfully carry out CTI functions, if they receive appropriate training and orientation to the domain [10][11][12]. In addition, new types of cyber threats coupled with hybrid threats involving misinformation, cybercrime sponsored by governments, and political manipulation of information [13] have increased the variety of knowledge needed by CTI analysts. These developments make it even more important to include people with different academic backgrounds [6][14].

As the threat landscape grows more complex and intertwined with social, political, and psychological dimensions, there is a growing need to clearly establish the disciplinary foundations that support the CTI profession. This study explores which multidisciplinary pathways can address the CTI skills gap and it is guided by two research questions: (RQ1) What core knowledge areas and transferable skills are aligned with career roles in CTI? (RQ2) Which academic disciplines relate to the core CTI knowledge areas and transferable skills?

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 outlines the methodology adopted to address the research questions. Section 3 presents the background and related work. Section 4 synthesizes the findings and Section 5 discusses the implications for academia, industry and policy makers, identifies the limitations of the study and provides future research directions. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 Methodology

This study employed a literature-based methodology to investigate how non-technical disciplines contribute to the field of CTI, with a particular focus on relevant knowledge areas and transferable skills. To address the research questions, the study was conducted in two phases. First, a preliminary literature review was undertaken to identify prominent disciplines that have demonstrated relevance to CTI practice. Initial results indicated five potential disciplines: criminology, psychology, political science, journalism, and data science. Then a comprehensive review of peer-reviewed publications, industry reports, white papers, and skills frameworks was conducted to identify how CTI is practiced and how the identified academic disciplines can contribute to CTI functions. Two skills frameworks were selected to facilitate the multidisciplinary investigations: the European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF) developed by ENISA [15], and the Mandiant CTI Analyst Core Competencies Framework [16]. These frameworks were leveraged to identify and categorize CTI knowledge areas and transferable skills that are foundational to professional CTI roles. This step ensured that the disciplinary contributions were evaluated against industry-aligned expectations and role definitions.

3 Background and Related Work

3.1 Skills Frameworks relevant to CTI

ENISA's European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF) defines 12 typical cybersecurity professional role profiles and details their associated responsibilities, skills, and knowledge. The framework profiles the role of a Cyber Threat Intelligence Specialist, providing valuable insights into the specific functions, knowledge domains, and skillsets required to collect, analyze, and disseminate actionable threat intelligence. Complementing this, the Mandiant Cyber Threat Intelligence Analyst Core Competencies Framework [16] offers a practitioner-oriented perspective, emphasizing the competencies essential for day-to-day CTI operations. It organizes the required capabilities into four pillars: problem solving, professional effectiveness, technical literacy, and cyber threat proficiency. For each pillar it elaborates on the underlying knowledge, skills, and attitudes that CTI analysts must develop. This includes not only technical literacy and threat modeling expertise but also emphasizes the transferable skills needed. Together, the ECSF and Mandiant frameworks provide a comprehensive foundation for understanding the multidimensional nature of the CTI role and serve as a reference point for mapping academic disciplines to CTI knowledge areas and skill. The following sections synthesize information from ENISA's and Mandiant's frameworks to identify core knowledge areas and transferable skills that are relevant to CTI.

3.2 CTI Knowledge Areas

CTI is the practice of collecting, analyzing, and disseminating information about current and emerging cyber threats to support informed decision-making and proactive

defense [15][16]. Its core mission is to transform raw data into actionable insights that help organizations anticipate, detect, and respond to malicious activity, whether it originates from cybercriminal groups, nation-state actors, or other adversaries. CTI operates at tactical, operational, and strategic levels, enabling both technical teams and executive leadership to understand the threat landscape, assess risks, and align security measures with organizational goals.

CTI is a multifaceted domain that draws upon a broad and diverse range of knowledge areas to support the identification, analysis, and mitigation of cyber threats. At its core, CTI relies on a solid foundation in **computing and cybersecurity fundamental principles**. Practitioners must have a thorough understanding of computer networks security, operating system architectures, the attack vectors utilized, and the common vulnerabilities exploited by adversaries. This technical proficiency is essential for identifying indicators of compromise (IoCs), interpreting security logs, analyzing malware and understanding how systems can be infiltrated or manipulated.

In addition to technical knowledge, CTI specialists should demonstrate **threat landscape situational awareness**. This knowledge area requires possessing deep understanding of threat actor types, from nation-states to cybercriminal groups, and their varying motivations, capabilities, and typical targets. Moreover, to understand how they conduct their operations, it is crucial to understand threat actor behavior, particularly the tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs) employed during cyber-attacks. Familiarity with threat modelling frameworks such as MITRE ATT&CK, the Diamond Model, and the Cyber Kill Chain, as well as an understanding of adversarial objectives, ranging from financial gain to political disruption, is essential for attributing activity and anticipating future behavior. As we navigate an era marked by hybrid threats, where cyber operations are often intertwined with political, economic, and military strategies, CTI practitioners must also be able to assess how geopolitical developments influence cyber activity. For instance, escalating tensions between states or military conflicts frequently coincide with shifts in targeting patterns, threat actor narratives, and the deployment of influence or disruption campaigns. Understanding the geopolitical context allows CTI analysts to better anticipate changes in threat posture, link cyber operations to broader strategic objectives, and deliver intelligence that supports both technical defence and strategic decision-making.

CTI also relies heavily on **intelligence analysis methodologies**, many of which are derived from traditional intelligence tradecraft. Intelligence analysis methodologies provide the conceptual and procedural foundation for producing reliable and actionable intelligence. CTI practitioners must demonstrate knowledge of the intelligence lifecycle, including the distinct phases of direction, collection, processing, analysis, dissemination, and feedback. They should be familiar with structured analytic techniques, such as key assumptions checks, alternative competing hypotheses, and root cause analysis, which help reduce cognitive bias and enhance analytical rigor. In addition, they must understand how to translate stakeholder concerns into well-formed intelligence requirements and how to align data collection efforts accordingly. Furthermore, CTI analysts are expected to be knowledgeable about threat modelling frameworks to support adversary tracking and intrusion analysis. This knowledge area enables practitioners to

contextualize data, identify patterns of malicious activity, and produce intelligence that can support decision-making at tactical, operational, and strategic levels.

A significant portion of CTI work involves the use of **open-source intelligence (OSINT)**. OSINT constitutes a vital knowledge area in CTI, encompassing the systematic collection and analysis of publicly available data to identify emerging threats, actor behaviors, and indicators of compromise. CTI practitioners must have a solid understanding of the types of OSINT sources, including domain registration records, social media platforms, dark web forums, breach data repositories, code repositories (e.g., GitHub), and technical blogs. They should be familiar with OSINT collection tools and platforms and Google Dorking techniques. Knowledge of how to safely navigate and extract information from the dark web, including the use of Tor and anonymization techniques, is also essential. Additionally, they should be aware of techniques for correlating and enriching open-source findings with proprietary threat intelligence to generate contextualized and relevant insights.

Beyond these core areas, an understanding of **Legal, Ethical, and Privacy Considerations** is increasingly important as CTI practitioners must navigate the legal and ethical implications of intelligence gathering and analysis. Familiarity with data protection regulations, national and international cyber laws, and organizational policies is essential to ensure that intelligence activities are compliant and ethically sound. This is particularly relevant when dealing with issues such as attribution, proactive threat hunting, or the use of deception.

Finally, the practical application of CTI relies on **Tools and Technologies**. This knowledge area encompasses competences in scripting languages such as Python, ability to interact with APIs, understanding and utilizing Threat Intelligence Platforms (TIPs), that rely on data standards like STIX and TAXII, for managing and analyzing threat data, as well as familiarity with Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) systems and their integration with threat intelligence. Proficiency in malware analysis tools, network analysis tools, and general data analysis tools is also essential for the day-to-day operations of a CTI professional.

3.3 Transferable skills relevant to CTI

CTI is a domain that thrives on the integration of diverse skill sets, many of which are not exclusive to technical disciplines. While domain-specific knowledge in cybersecurity is fundamental, CTI also heavily relies on a range of transferable skills. These skills can be acquired in other academic or professional contexts and adapted to the CTI role. The combination of the ECSF Cyber Threat Intelligence Specialist role profile and the Mandiant CTI Analyst Competencies Framework provides a comprehensive picture of the core transferable skills necessary for success in this evolving discipline.

One of the most critical transferable skills is **critical thinking**, which demonstrates the ability to evaluate complex and often incomplete information, synthesize findings, and produce actionable insights. The Mandiant framework explicitly emphasizes structured analytic techniques, alternative hypothesis development, and cognitive bias mitigation. Similarly, the ECSF profile highlights the need for analytical and modelling

capabilities to interpret threat actor behavior and develop risk-based recommendations. A high degree of critical thinking is necessary to effectively perform these tasks.

Closely tied to critical thinking is the ability to perform **research and analysis**. CTI professionals must be adept at formulating intelligence requirements, identifying relevant data sources, and analyzing information to uncover patterns, correlations, and anomalies. Mandiant's framework describes research as spanning a variety of data types, from host-based logs to darknet activity, and notes the value of familiarity with data visualization and programming tools. Proficiency in data analysis, including the collection, cleaning, processing, and statistical interpretation of information, is essential. The capacity to perform pivot analysis, identifying connections between seemingly disparate data points, and understanding the complexities of attribution, the process of linking attacks to specific actors, are also key components of this area.

Another essential skill is the **investigative mindset**, which is slightly distinct from analytical thinking. It involves curiosity, perseverance, and the ability to develop hypotheses in the face of uncertainty. CTI analysts with an investigative mindset are naturally inclined to dig deeper, challenge assumptions, and pursue leads that may initially appear insignificant. This mindset supports pattern recognition in threat actor behavior and the identification of novel or evolving attack vectors, particularly in complex or ambiguous datasets. In CTI, where adversaries continually shift tactics and obfuscate their actions, the ability to "connect the dots" across disconnected or partial indicators is invaluable. Moreover, the investigative mindset enables analysts to maintain focus during long, iterative inquiry processes, to adapt their methodology when conventional paths yield limited results, and to maintain a sense of objective detachment even when pursuing high-impact cases. Ultimately, an investigative mindset enables forward-looking intelligence that not only explains current threat activity but also predicts shifts in adversary tactics, generating insights to support strategic decision-making and long-term cyber resilience.

Time management and organization are essential transferable skills for CTI professionals, as the nature of the role often involves juggling multiple tasks, data sources, and competing priorities. CTI analysts are frequently required to monitor real-time developments, respond to intelligence requests, update their threat analysis and produce reports under tight deadlines, all while navigating large volumes of technical and contextual information. Effective time management allows analysts to triage incoming data, prioritize threats based on potential impact and urgency, and allocate their efforts efficiently across tactical, operational, and strategic tasks. In parallel, strong organizational skills are critical for maintaining well-structured intelligence notes, preserving the origin of sources, and tracking investigative leads. These organizational habits also facilitate transparency and reproducibility in analytic workflows, which are essential for maintaining credibility within CTI teams and when engaging with stakeholders.

Communication is a core transferable competency in CTI that cannot be overlooked. Threat intelligence is valuable only when it is clearly and effectively communicated to its intended audience, whether they are technical teams, business leaders, or policymakers. Analysts must be able to write concise and actionable reports, present findings visually when needed, and articulate recommendations with appropriate confidence levels and clearly stated assumptions. The Mandiant framework highlights the

importance of presenting findings clearly and effectively to different audiences, from highly technical stakeholders to executive leadership. Writing skills, narrative construction, probabilistic reasoning, and audience adaptation are all critical in producing effective intelligence reports and briefings. The ECSF profile similarly emphasizes the need to "articulate and communicate intelligence openly and publicly at all levels."

Professional effectiveness also features prominently, including transferable skills such as **teamwork**, **emotional intelligence**, and the ability to operate within organizational and cross-functional structures. CTI work often involves collaboration with incident responders, legal teams, policy makers, and external information-sharing groups. The Mandiant framework emphasizes emotional intelligence and business acumen, noting that CTI professionals must understand organizational priorities and translate threat data into risk-relevant insights.

From a technical standpoint, technical literacy is a necessary competency, but aspects of it, such as familiarity with enterprise IT environments, digital hygiene, or networking, can be taught and acquired through structured training or certification programs. The ability to learn new tools and adapt to evolving technologies is more critical than prior technical mastery. This means individuals from non-STEM fields can transition into CTI roles if they possess **adaptability and a life-long learning mindset** which will enable them to effectively reskill in new career pathways.

Lastly, **cultural awareness and linguistic skills** are increasingly important in CTI, especially when monitoring foreign threat actor activity or analyzing global cyber operations. The ECSF indirectly supports this through its emphasis on identifying "non-cyber events with implications on cyber-related activities." Mandiant notes that language proficiency, cultural literacy, and geopolitical awareness are valuable for contextualizing threat activity, especially in OSINT or nation-state threat analysis.

3.4 Academic Disciplines Contributing to CTI

The preliminary literature investigations performed in the context of this work showed that disciplines such as criminology, psychology, political science, journalism, and data science contribute essential knowledge and skills to support core CTI functions [3][11].

Criminology plays a prominent role in extending CTI beyond its technical foundations. Hoffman et al. [17] illustrate how life-course criminology and behavioral modeling can be used to understand and forecast cybercriminal behavior. Their study on hacker trajectories reveals that early indicators such as social visibility and ideological motives can help predict long-term threat levels. This insight emphasizes the necessity of criminological methods in profiling and tracking threat actors. Similarly, Jacob et al. [18] apply theories like Routine Activity and Situational Crime Prevention to analyze the societal factors influencing cyber threats. They argue that integrating behavioral and legal theories into CTI can enhance the prediction of cybercrime trends and inform preventive strategies. The systematic review by Bada and Nurse [19] reinforces this approach, showing how personality models and psychological motivations shape offender behavior and should be part of intelligence assessments.

Psychology is equally central to effective CTI work. Rich and Aiken [8] propose a behavioral model that integrates digital forensics with forensic psychology to better

understand the motives and tactics of cybercriminals. Their research highlights how psychological profiling, scenario analysis, and forensic reasoning contribute to identifying emerging threats before they materialize. Dawson and Thomson [20] also stress the importance of cognitive adaptability, communication, and human behavior awareness, arguing that success in CTI relies on more than technical knowledge. These views align with Kesler's work [11], which advocates for a broader integration of behavioral and ethical considerations in CTI roles. By proposing a framework that spans psychology, ethics, and law, Kesler encourages cybersecurity professionals to adopt a more reflective and people-focused mindset when analyzing threats.

Political science contributes a strategic and contextual layer to CTI, particularly in cases involving nation-state cyber operations. Bardakis [1] traces CTI's intellectual roots to military science, international relations, and intelligence studies. His work emphasizes that strategic intelligence demands awareness of geopolitical dynamics, which are traditionally explored in political science and policy studies. Lavorgna [6] extends this line of thinking by offering a typology of state-enabled cybercrimes, highlighting how political coercion, disinformation, and ideological warfare are intertwined with digital threats. This requires CTI practitioners to consider national interests, propaganda strategies, and institutional motivations. Donaldson and Morkel [21] further support this claim by presenting CTI as a socio-technical field, advocating for the integration of political theory and public policy into the analysis of complex threats such as misinformation and state-sponsored cyberattacks.

Journalism, although less frequently cited in traditional cybersecurity literature, contributes significant value to CTI through investigative and communication skills. Nickels [10] presents real-world examples of professionals with backgrounds in journalism and intelligence analysis successfully transitioning into CTI roles. These individuals demonstrate strong competencies in source validation, narrative construction, and contextual analysis. These capabilities are critical for developing intelligence products that are accurate, actionable, and clearly communicated. Ademola and Somorin [22] also identify journalism as a contributing discipline, particularly in the intelligence cycle's phases of information gathering and dissemination.

Data science is essential to CTI in both operational and strategic contexts. This discipline enables the development of models for threat detection, behavior clustering, and the automation of intelligence workflows. Saeed et al. [3] provide a broad review of CTI applications, noting that machine learning, anomaly detection, and natural language processing techniques drawn from data science are at the core of threat actor classification and risk prediction. Xu et al. [23] reinforce this view by documenting the integration of real-time analytics, forensic models, and behavior-based detection in CTI systems. Their work highlights the need for CTI professionals to possess both quantitative analysis skills and an understanding of the environment in which threat data emerges. Furthermore, Hoffman et al. [17] show how statistical techniques such as group-based trajectory modeling can reveal patterns in attacker behavior over time, combining data-driven methods with behavioral insight.

Collectively, these five disciplines each contribute to and can strengthen CTI operations. These disciplinary foundations form the basis of this study and reinforce the case

for exploring non-technical pathways into CTI careers as both necessary and strategically valuable to create a broader CTI talent pipeline.

4 Synthesis of Disciplinary Contributions to CTI

This section synthesizes the insights gathered from the investigations, and critically interprets how criminology, psychology, political science, journalism, and data science can contribute to the CTI field. Two tables have been constructed to facilitate the discussion; a discipline takes a tick on a cell if it can contribute to a knowledge area (Table I) or if it exhibits the relevant transferable skill (Table II).

Table I: Key CTI knowledge areas

CTI Knowledge Area	Criminology	Psychology	Political Science	Journalism	Data Science
Computing and Cybersecurity Technical Literacy	✓				✓
Threat Landscape Situational Awareness	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Intelligence Analysis Methodologies	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
OSINT	✓		✓	✓	✓
Legal, Ethical, and Privacy Considerations	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Tools and Technologies	✓				✓

The synthesis of the findings related to the core CTI knowledge areas that the five academic disciplines can contribute (Table I), reveal important insights that reinforce the inherently multidisciplinary nature of CTI. Each discipline contributes to the field in different ways, with varying degrees of relevance across the key knowledge areas.

The area of computing and cybersecurity technical literacy is strongly supported by data science, which provides foundational computational thinking, scripting, and data modeling skills that are increasingly critical in threat detection and intelligence workflows. While this discipline may not engage directly with traditional cybersecurity frameworks, its technical depth aligns with operational CTI tasks, especially those involving automation or machine learning [3]. Criminology, though not a technical field, can also contribute to this area through its integration of digital forensics and an understanding of cybercrime tools. The remaining disciplines (psychology, political science, and journalism) typically do not provide direct support in this area.

In contrast, the knowledge area of threat landscape situational awareness demonstrates high relevance across all five disciplines. Political science offers strategic insights into threat actor behavior, especially in relation to nation-state operations, ideological warfare, and geopolitical conflict [1]. Criminology and psychology provide theoretical and empirical frameworks [8] [17] to understand offender motivations and escalation dynamics, both critical elements for profiling and forecasting threat actor activity. Journalism contributes by contextualizing cyber and hybrid threats within

broader social and political developments [13], skills that are crucial for identifying and understanding the non-technical dimensions of cyber threats. Data science supports trend detection and threat clustering at scale, enriching situational understanding with statistical precision [17].

Intelligence analysis methodologies also emerge as a prominent multidisciplinary domain. Political science, criminology, and psychology contribute long-established traditions in both qualitative and quantitative reasoning, scenario analysis, and structured hypothesis testing. Journalism offers practical investigative strategies for research, source evaluation, and tracing the dissemination of false information to detect influence operations, which align closely with intelligence analysis tasks [10]. Data science brings computational analysis, visualization, and pattern discovery capabilities that further elevate analytic depth and speed [23].

The field of OSINT further illustrates the multidisciplinary nature of CTI. Journalism provides the clearest methodological foundation, with skills in information discovery, validation, and responsible reporting [22]. Political science contributes by analyzing disinformation campaigns, influence operations, and media manipulation [1] [6]. Criminologists engage with OSINT to understand offender behavior, digital criminal ecosystems, and the social dynamics of cybercrime communities [17]. Their insights provide valuable guidance as to how and where cybercriminals operate online, including forums, marketplaces, and social platforms. Data science, meanwhile, can facilitate large-scale OSINT operations through web scraping, entity extraction, and natural language processing [3], tools that are indispensable in modern CTI practice.

Legal, ethical, and privacy considerations are another knowledge domain that benefits from contributions across all five disciplines. Criminology and political science support this area through their grounding in legal systems, international law, and policy studies. Psychology introduces ethical sensitivity in adversary profiling and in the analysis of human behavior under surveillance. Journalism reinforces norms around transparency, source protection, and the public interest, values that are relevant when disseminating threat intelligence. Data science, finally, brings awareness of algorithmic fairness, data privacy, and the ethical implications of automated decision-making.

The final knowledge area, tools and technologies, is most closely aligned with data science, given its technical emphasis on scripting, APIs, and analytics platforms [16]. Criminology also contributes in contexts where digital tools are used in investigations or forensic analysis. However, this area remains the most discipline-specific, highlighting a likely gap for professionals entering CTI from other disciplines. Upskilling in this area may therefore be a key requirement for multidisciplinary CTI career pathways.

Table II further affirms the central role that non-technical disciplines can play in shaping well-rounded CTI professionals. Unlike technical knowledge areas, where disciplinary contributions are uneven, the development of transferable skills is far more broadly distributed, with most of the examined disciplines exhibiting strong alignment across the skills spectrum.

Critical thinking is a cornerstone of all five disciplines. Criminology and psychology foster this through their analytical approaches to behavior, deviance, and intervention strategies. Political science emphasizes critical engagement with systems, ideologies, and policy, often in complex, ambiguous environments. Journalism requires critical

evaluation of sources and events, ensuring accuracy and objectivity in public reporting [24]. Data science, though technical in nature, cultivates critical reasoning through hypothesis testing, model evaluation, and data interpretation.

Table II: Key CTI Transferable skills

Transferable Skill	Crimi- nology	Psy- chology	Po- litical Science	Jour- nalism	Data Science
Critical Thinking	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Research and Analysis	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Investigative Mindset	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Time Management and Organization	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Communication	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Teamwork	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Emotional Intelligence	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Adaptability	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Life-long Learning Mindset	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cultural Awareness and Linguistic Skills	✓	✓	✓	✓	

Research and analysis skills are equally present across all five fields. Criminology and political science are rooted in investigative inquiry, supported by both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. Psychology’s emphasis on experimental design, behavioral data, and interpretive frameworks makes it a natural contributor to structured analysis. Journalists, trained to investigate, verify, and contextualize information, demonstrate these skills in highly applied ways. Data scientists engage in rigorous data-driven inquiry, designing pipelines and models to extract actionable insights from complex datasets, skills directly applicable to intelligence workflows [25].

The investigative mindset is prominent in criminology, psychology, and journalism, where patterns of behavior, causality, and intention are explored. Criminologists analyze offender trajectories and motivation, while psychologists examine mental models, decision-making, and behavioral triggers. Journalists conduct deep-dive investigations, often with limited and fragmented information, a process mirroring the way CTI analysts piece together threat intelligence from open sources [26]. Political science contributes a similar mindset through strategic scenario modeling and policy analysis.

Time management and organization are universally practiced across all disciplines, though the emphasis may vary. Criminology, psychology, and political science typically involve structured research projects, case studies, or fieldwork requiring long-term planning and documentation. Journalists operate under tight deadlines, balancing multiple assignments while maintaining accurate records of sources and findings. Data science demands project management, version control, and the organization of code, datasets, and results, skills critical to reproducible intelligence workflows.

Communication skills are strongly developed in political science and journalism, where clarity, persuasion, and audience adaptation are core elements. Psychology and criminology also train individuals to explain complex behavioral phenomena to both

expert and non-expert audiences, while data science increasingly requires the translation of analytical outcomes into accessible insights for decision-makers. Across disciplines, the ability to write clearly, present findings, and tailor messages to different stakeholders [27] aligns with the communication needs of CTI.

Teamwork is consistently cultivated in all disciplines. Psychology and criminology often involve multi-agency cooperation, while journalism is typically embedded in newsroom environments requiring coordination and shared editorial responsibility. In data science, teamwork is central to agile development, cross-functional analysis, and model deployment. Political science also involves negotiation, consensus-building, and deliberative processes that mirror collaborative threat intelligence efforts [21].

Emotional intelligence is well developed in psychology and criminology. Both fields engage directly with human behavior in contexts that require empathy, self-awareness, and social insight. Political science and journalism also touch on this skill through their focus on public communication, diplomacy, and human-centered narratives.

Adaptability and a life-long learning mindset are embedded across all disciplines. The rapidly evolving nature of cyber threats necessitates a culture of continual upskilling and intellectual flexibility. Criminology, psychology, and journalism have to adapt [27] to changing social dynamics, new platforms, and emerging technologies that influence both criminal behavior and information dissemination. Political science responds to shifting geopolitical landscapes and the evolving role of cyber operations in international relations, while data science continually evolves alongside advances in algorithms, data privacy regulations, and analytical tools.

Finally, cultural awareness and linguistic skills are notably present in journalism, political science, psychology, and criminology. These disciplines require professionals to engage with diverse populations, interpret behaviors and communications within specific cultural contexts. In journalism, the ability to analyze narratives across languages and cultures is essential for monitoring global media and disinformation trends, which are key components of CTI in the age of hybrid threats [24]. Political science offers deep insights into geopolitical sensitivities and cross-cultural conflict dynamics, which are crucial for understanding the motivations and strategies of state and non-state threat actors. Psychology and criminology further reinforce this skill set by examining how cultural background influences behavior, including decision-making, radicalization, and online community dynamics. These capabilities enable CTI analysts to assess threats more accurately, especially when dealing with adversaries operating across linguistic and cultural boundaries.

5 Discussion

5.1 The Value of Multidisciplinary CTI Teams

Findings showcase that while no single discipline covers all CTI knowledge areas comprehensively, each discipline contributes meaningfully to multiple domains. The knowledge areas most central to effective CTI, such as threat landscape awareness, OSINT, and intelligence analysis, are supported by diverse academic disciplines. The

analysis also reveals a high degree of alignment between the core transferable skills required in CTI and the educational outcomes of a range of non-technical disciplines. Skills such as critical thinking, research and analysis, an investigative mindset, communication, time management and organisation are not only broadly cultivated but often deeply embedded in the professional identities of individuals trained outside traditional cybersecurity pathways [10][24][28]. This strong relevance to CTI highlights the importance of recognizing and valuing multidisciplinary talent that can contribute meaningfully to CTI operations. It also supports the broader argument that CTI is a multidisciplinary field, and the CTI community should actively seek talent from beyond the traditional technical disciplines.

The growing complexity of the cyber threat landscape increasingly demands CTI professionals who can bridge technical analysis with contextual interpretation, strategic thinking, and effective communication. Diverse teams with individuals who collectively combine technical competencies with expertise from disciplines such as criminology, psychology, political science, journalism, or data science, can bring a uniquely valuable perspective to CTI operations [27]. Rather than viewing non-technical backgrounds as a limitation, professionals originating from other disciplines can enhance threat intelligence by integrating behavioral, geopolitical, or narrative insights into otherwise technical assessments [1][6][8].

Moreover, diverse professionals can act as integrators within CTI teams, connecting different silos of expertise such as analysts, legal advisors, and policy specialists, and ensuring that intelligence outputs reflect not just technical indicators, but also strategic and organizational relevance [16]. Recognizing and nurturing multidisciplinary teams can thus improve the agility, diversity, and strategic capacity of CTI functions, and should be a priority for both hiring managers and educational institutions designing next-generation CTI education and training programs.

5.2 Rethinking CTI Education and Career Pathways

The findings of this study carry important implications for academia, industry and policy makers. There is a pressing need to rethink how CTI education and career pathways are structured, particularly to accommodate talent from non-technical disciplines [28]. Traditional workforce frameworks and cybersecurity training models tend to prioritize technical depth [29], such as malware analysis or network forensics, while undervaluing the analytical, behavioral, and contextual competencies that are equally critical for effective threat intelligence [30][31]. As the field evolves, there is a growing case for creating flexible, multidisciplinary pathways that allow professionals from criminology, psychology, political science, journalism, and data science to enter CTI roles through targeted upskilling. For example, a political science graduate may benefit from applied modules in threat modelling, OSINT, and CTI reporting. This reinforces the need for training pathways that can scaffold existing strengths from contributing disciplines to CTI while closing knowledge gaps in more technical areas such as tools and cybersecurity literacy [22][25]. Educational programs should consider designing modular curricula that map to frameworks like ECSF to provide structured learning and empower learners to build upon their existing strengths [15].

Hiring practices also tend to prioritize technical qualifications, inadvertently limiting the diversity and breadth of talent entering CTI roles. Recognizing the value of multidisciplinary expertise, particularly in areas such as behavioral analysis, geopolitical awareness, investigative reasoning, and strategic communication, requires a shift toward more inclusive, competency-based approaches [8][16]. Policymakers and workforce planners should consider extending skills frameworks such as ECSF to more explicitly acknowledge non-technical pathways and diverse roles within CTI. This includes revising job profiles, adapting qualification standards, and promoting cross-sector training schemes that facilitate entry from other fields beyond computing [24]. Organizations should be encouraged to adopt multidisciplinary hiring strategies and invest in role-specific upskilling programs that build on existing disciplinary strengths.

Rethinking career pathways, workforce development strategies and hiring practices will not only make CTI careers more accessible but can also broaden the talent pool, enhance diversity, and strengthen the resilience of CTI teams in addressing complex, multi-domain threats.

5.3 Study Limitations and Future Research

While this study provides a structured synthesis of disciplinary contributions to CTI knowledge and skills, it is primarily based on an initial literature analysis. It does not include empirical data which may reveal additional insights in role expectations, career transitions, or organizational barriers. The selection of the five disciplines was grounded in initial literature review and is not exhaustive; other fields may also offer valuable contributions to CTI. Future research will involve deeper literature review and analysis of empirical data to validate and extend these mappings.

6 Conclusions

This study explored the contributions of non-technical disciplines (criminology, psychology, political science, journalism, and data science) to CTI. Through a structured synthesis of existing literature, the study has shown that while these disciplines may not traditionally fall within the cybersecurity domain, they each provide valuable and often underutilized competences that can meaningfully strengthen CTI operations.

The analysis demonstrated that many of the core CTI knowledge areas, particularly threat landscape situational awareness, intelligence analysis methodologies, and open-source intelligence, are supported by multidisciplinary expertise. Additionally, the transferable skills that CTI roles demand, such as critical thinking, investigative ability, communication, critical thinking, and adaptability, are broadly cultivated across the disciplines studied. These findings challenge the narrow perception of CTI as a predominantly technical field and highlight the potential of multidisciplinary CTI teams.

However, structural barriers continue to limit the integration of non-technical professionals into CTI. Addressing these challenges will require a rethinking of educational pathways, hiring practices, and professional development models. This includes creating modular, role-specific training that leverages existing disciplinary strengths

while bridging knowledge gaps. Adopting more inclusive competency frameworks that recognize a wider range of entry points into the CTI workforce is essential to empower academia, industry and policy makers to diversify the talent pipeline.

In an era marked by hybrid threats, geopolitical instability, and increasingly sophisticated cyber operations, the need for multidimensional intelligence capabilities is greater than ever. By embracing multidisciplinary approaches and expanding the CTI talent pipeline, organizations and educators can foster a more diverse, adaptable, and effective intelligence workforce capable of addressing the full complexity of modern cyber threats. Ultimately, building a diverse and resilient CTI workforce depends on a shift in both mindset and practice. Organizations, educators, and policymakers must collaborate to break down the disciplinary boundaries that limit talent mobility and design flexible, inclusive pathways that equip professionals from varied backgrounds to contribute meaningfully to the future of cyber threat intelligence.

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